

Utilizing Library Resources by Teachers and Students at Dronacharya College of Engineering, Greater Noida: A Survey

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the awareness, use, satisfaction and problems regarding the available library resources at Dronacharya College of Engineering. In this study, the perspectives of teachers and students were compared side by side. To collect data from 400 targeted samples (350 students and 50 teachers) with the help of a structured questionnaire designed to cover all possible aspects required to fulfil the study objectives using the descriptive survey method. Based on the responses of 236 valid respondents (59.00%), it can be inferred that although the library offers a sizable collection of print and electronic resources, it is somewhat short on valued and updated materials. Besides, students put the internet facility into serious question. Overall, the teachers are neutrally satisfied with the collection and the students are satisfied enough. Updated collection, demand driven acquisition, expanded internet access, and awareness campaigns are just a few suggested actions that could improve user satisfaction and the effective use of library resources.

Keywords: Library resources, Resource utilization, Library users, User satisfaction, User awareness, Dronacharya College of Engineering (DCE)

INTRODUCTION

The fundamental function of college libraries is to support the institution's teaching, learning, and research activities

and assist in achieving its objective and goal. College libraries are regarded as the hub of information transmission. A college library's main goal is to improve the calibre, depth, diversity, and timeliness of its resources to support the curriculum of the institution [1]. The materials that libraries offer - textbooks, reference books, dictionaries, encyclopaedias, journals, theses, conference proceedings, bibliographies, and directories - serve the needs of their patrons. Libraries began creating online resources and subscribing to cutting-edge databases in the ICT era to expand the scope of their resources.

Acquiring a resource is not a library's prime objective but ensuring its use. The usage analysis of any library is an essential task because that provides the actual value of the present collection to the users and requirements for future collection development. The present study tries to evaluate the utilization of library resources by the student and teachers of the Dronacharya College of Engineering (DCE). To know the perspective of both types of potential users (students & teachers), every possible parameter related to the utilization of library resources is included in the survey questionnaire.

ABOUT THE INSTITUTION AND THE TARGET LIBRARY

Established in 2006 and approved by AICTE (the All India Council for Technical Education), the Dronacharya College of Engineering (DCE) is a premier institute that is affiliated with Uttar-Pradesh Technical, University (UPTU). Building over 50,000 sq ft in the heart of Greater Noida (NCR), the institute is providing a dynamic learning environment in response to the changing needs of society. This institute aims at developing a centre for excellence in Management and Information Technology, thrust areas of education, training, research and consultancy. The institute offers full-time MCA, MBA, and B-Tech programmes. The Institute boasts a cutting-edge infrastructure that includes a computer centre with air conditioning, a library, an auditorium, and seminar rooms. OHPs, LCDs, and whiteboards, among other technologies, are all present in the classrooms. DCE is now regarded as one of the top universities in the NCR, thanks to its outstanding teaching staff.

DCE institute library (Information Resource Centre, IRC) was established in 2006, starting from the institute's establishment [2]. The DCE Library is spread over 2800 sq. ft of area and provides stimulation to young minds. It has been systematically and steadily strengthened. The IRC's operation and services are fully computerized with "e-Granthalaya" multi-user Integrated Library Automation Software, developed by National Informatics Centre, New Delhi and a Bar Code-based circulation system [3]. The IRC is equipped with 34038 volumes of books (5056 titles) from different streams. Besides these texts and reference books, IRC is also subscribing to 87 national and 56 international print journals, magazines and dailies. Additionally, the DCE library has subscribed to four (4) databases of e-resources, i.e. IEL Online, ASME (including AMR), InfoTrac Engineering Collection (IEC) and Global Periodicals.com [4]. Bibliographic records of IRC's holdings can be accessed through

the e-Granthalaya's On-Line Public Access Catalogue (OPAC). The IRC also maintains a good collection of essential educational CDs on Engineering & Technology. The college is an institutional member of DELNET and the British Council Library.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Numerous studies on awareness and usage of library resources have been done from a similar angle. In order to establish the context for this specific research, a few of them are reviewed here.

Prasannath (2015) [5] randomly chose 180 students from national schools in all four educational zones in Batticaloa, Sri Lanka, to assess their library awareness, visit frequency, and use. The researcher's structured questionnaire found that 40% of students utilised the library to review their own notes, 70% were satisfied with the content, and the majority used the library's books and magazines. The lack of relevant practice books was the biggest issue. The study advises using audio-visual and electronic resources to improve library use. Gurikar (2018) [6] examined library users from 46 major institutions in India to determine how widely social media is used based on popularity and specialised applications. The study described how libraries use social media to serve their users. Kalyani and Thanuskodi (2019) [7] studied the usage of library resources among civil service library aspirants. In this survey maximum number of respondents (59%) were engineering graduates. The study revealed that candidates possess good information awareness regarding the announcements, eligibility and preparatory materials. Similarly, M and R (2019) [8] studied the use of library resources and information services at Alagappa University library from 90 respondent students and research scholars with the help of a 13 questions structured questionnaire. Amedu (2021) [9] used a correlational design to explain Economics students' behavioural intention and usage of online libraries using social influence, self-efficacy, perceived

utility, perceived ease of use, and attitude. A total of 150 students from five South East Nigerian universities were randomly selected to complete self-report questionnaires. The study indicated that a recursive model best explained students' behaviour and online library use. Attitude, reported ease of use, and perceived usefulness were the main predictors of online library use among postgraduate Economics students. Veer and Panda (2021) [10] focused on the usage of e-resources in the Chandigarh University library during the pandemic period. An online survey was conducted by collecting data from 158 respondents (students, faculties & staff). The majority of CU Library users know about and use e-Resources for their specific needs, according to the statistics. The study also discusses students' and faculties' e-resource access and utility issues. Matonkar and Dhuri (2021) [11] investigated how six Goa college libraries used their resources and services. A well-structured Google questionnaire garnered 300 replies for examination. The majority of users (91.33%) choose to borrow books from the library. The study found that inadequate library resources were the biggest issue for users. Goa libraries benefit from 68.67% of users being satisfied with library resources. This study suggested marketing library services raise user awareness and utilisation. Abdullah and Yusuf (2022) [12] examined the change in library usage after the adaptation of demand driven acquisition (DDA) model in Malaysian academic libraries. A quantitative research survey was conducted to collect data from 152 respondents. Ani et al. (2022) [13] investigated undergraduate students' use of library resources for academic activity in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Purposive sampling was used to choose 30 UG students from each of the four university departments that were chosen for the study. According to the research, the library has enough resources, and students frequently utilise its books and references for consultation. Oghenetega and Eireyi-Fidelis

(2022) [14] investigated the usage of electronic academic database resources by lecturers and postgraduate students at Western Delta University, Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria. A descriptive design was adopted to study 134 lecturers and postgraduate students at WDU. The results demonstrated that postgraduate students and lecturers had a high level of awareness of and use of electronic academic databases. Olanusi and Edward (2022) [15] investigated the usage of university library-based electronic resources by undergraduates at Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, and Ondo State, Nigeria. A descriptive questionnaire design was developed to evaluate 130 responded undergraduates. The findings revealed that the majority of the respondents use university library electronic resources twice a week mainly for class assignments and preparation of class seminars.

STUDY OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study were to know:

- (i) Frequency of the library users visit in the IRC
- (ii) Awareness level and medium of awareness of the library users about the available library resources
- (iii) Purpose of use library resources by the library users
- (iv) Most favourite location of accessing library resources
- (v) Frequency of use library resources by different type of document and resource
- (vi) Frequency of use different E-resources
- (vii) Satisfaction level with the available library resources
- (viii) Problem faced by the users during use of library resources

In this study the potential library users are the teachers and students of DCE. A survey was conducted with a structured questionnaire aiming at collect responses from the users about the above mentioned objectives.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the research is to determine the information needs of the users - primarily teachers and students at DCE - and the degree to which the library's collection can meet those needs. A structured questionnaire was designed and distributed to DCE teachers and students in order to determine user needs. Potential users, i.e. students and teachers are selected as a sample of the study rather than library professionals because they can provide the exact picture of the resources and services they received from the DCE library [16]. The questionnaire included closed-ended questions with predetermined options to restrict the coverage region of the study. To check the authenticity of the responses, in addition to distributing questionnaires,

whenever possible brief interviews were also conducted.

SAMPLE IDENTIFICATION AND DATA COLLECTION

Dronacharya College of Engineering consist of the six main branches, e.g. Computer Science Engineering (CSE), Information Technology (IT), Electronics and Communications Engineering (ECE), Mechanical and Industrial Engineering (MIE), Management Business Administration (MBA) and Master of Computer Application (MCA). The population for the study consists of teachers and students of this six branches of DCE, which are almost 1500 in number. A stratified random sample of 400 (Teachers=50, Students=350) was selected to distribute the questionnaire.

Table 1: Category-wise Distribution of Questionnaire

Category	Questionnaire Distribution	Relevant Response	Percentage
Teachers	50	50	100.00%
Students	350	186	53.14%
Total	400	236	59.00%

The DCE teachers have been very supportive of this study, and all 50 of the distributed questionnaires have been fully filled out and, in some cases, returned right away. Only 186 (53.14%) of the 350 sent

questionnaires for students were chosen for the final study, even though more than 200 were returned owing to incomplete, incorrectly filled, or other concerns.

Table 2: Stream-wise Distribution of Questionnaire

Stream	CSE		IT		ECE		MIE		MBA		MCA	
	T	S	T	S	T	S	T	S	T	S	T	S
Category												
Distribution	13	80	4	50	10	60	7	50	10	60	6	50
Response	13	41	4	23	10	37	7	30	10	29	6	26
Response Percentage	100%	51.25%	100%	46%	100%	61.67%	100%	60%	100%	48.34%	100%	52%

*T = Teachers, S = Students

Teachers in all streams have a 100% response rate if the respondents are further divided by the stream, as shown in Table 2. The ECE department had the highest response rate (61.67%) across academic departments, followed by MIE (60%) and MCA (52%) departments.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

The data were collected, tabulated for better understanding on tally sheets, and then cleaned in Microsoft Excel for better

visualization. Several parameters that were specified in the questionnaire were used to assess the results to accomplish the targeted outcomes. In order to achieve the study's objectives, the analytic process is result-oriented and primarily percentage-based.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Frequency of Visit in the Library:

The number of instances in which individuals visited the library is shown in Table 3. It reveals the awareness and

reading preferences of the patrons in a library setting. It is clear that among the respondents, 62% (31) of teachers often visited the library, whereas 12% (6) of respondents rarely attended. Currently,

65.05% (121) of the 186 students who responded to the survey visited the library always, and no student reported never going there.

Table 3: Frequency of Visit the Library

User Type	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Teachers (n%, n=50)	8 (16.00%)	31 (62.00%)	5 (10.00%)	6 (12.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Students (n%, n=186)	121 (65.05%)	48 (25.81%)	17 (9.14%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Overall (n%, n=236)	129 (54.66%)	79 (33.48%)	22 (9.32%)	6 (2.54%)	0 (0.00%)

This outcome indicated that both the students and teachers have a good attitude toward using the library, making it easier to make the most of its resources, improve its services, and develop more collections in line with user needs.

Awareness about Library Resources:

Table 4 displays the awareness level of the respondents about the available library resources. The majority of teachers who responded were split between being almost aware (30%) and being partially aware (56%). However, the majority of students who responded chose between being fully aware (32.8%) and almost aware (66.13%).

Table 4: Awareness about Library Resources

User Type	Fully	Almost	Partially	Only Some	Not at All
Teachers (n%, n=50)	4 (8.00%)	15 (30.00%)	28 (56.00%)	3 (6.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Students (n%, n=186)	61 (32.80%)	123 (66.13%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.07%)	0 (0.00%)
Overall (n%, n=236)	65 (27.54%)	138 (58.48%)	28 (11.86%)	5 (2.12%)	0 (0.00%)

Almost all of the resources that are available in the library are generally known to the patrons. Every collection in the library must have every possibility to be used in accordance with the second and third laws of library science, which state that “every user his or her book” & “every book its reader”, respectively.

Medium of Awareness about Library Resources:

Table 5 provided information on the source via which the users get aware of the library

resources. This is a multi-answer question in the questionnaire, and users can choose more than one option. According to the received responses, all of the teachers (100%) choose personal effort as the most preferable medium and getting aware by colleagues (68%) is in the second position. On the other side, the students prefer library staff as their top awareness medium about library resources. Overall, the respondents prefer self-effort for their most preferable (97.88%) awareness medium.

Table 5: Awareness Medium about Library Resources

SN	Awareness Medium	Teachers (n%, n=50)	Students (n%, n=186)	Overall (n%, n=236)
1	Library Staff	17 (34.00%)	184 (98.92%)	201 (85.17%)
2	Library Brochure	0 (0.00%)	96 (51.61%)	96 (40.68%)
3	Library Website	6 (12.00%)	177 (95.16%)	183 (77.54%)
4	Library Notice Board	0 (0.00%)	73 (39.25%)	73 (30.93%)
5	Library Social Media Platform	0 (0.00%)	32 (17.20%)	32 (13.56%)
6	Several Library Programs	6 (12.00%)	25 (13.44%)	31 (13.14%)
7	From Colleagues/Classmates	34 (68.00%)	111 (59.68%)	144 (61.02%)
8	By Personal Effort	50 (100.00%)	181 (97.31%)	231 (97.88%)

Purpose of Use Library Resources:

Similar to the previous, this is also a multi-answer question. This inquiry seeks information about the preferred uses of library resources by both teachers and students.

(a) For Teachers

According to the responses, the teachers mostly used library resources for preparing lectures (100%) and for personal research (88%). The choice of using library resources for preparing exam questions (72%) and gaining new knowledge (68%) is also noticeable.

Table 6: Purpose of Use Library Resources (Teachers)

SN	Purposes	No. of Respondents	Percentage (n%, n=50)
1	For preparation of lecture	50	100.00%
2	For preparation of exam questions	36	72.00%
3	For personal research	44	88.00%
4	To select course reference resources	10	20.00%
5	For administrative work	0	0.00%
6	For gaining new knowledge	34	68.00%
7	To read in leisure time	7	14.00%
8	Others	0	0.00%

(b) For Students

The responses in Table 7 indicate that the students mostly used library resources for preparing their class notes (96.24%) and

exam preparation (87.63%). Additionally, it is noted that very few students (9.14%) use library resources for personal research.

Table 7: Purpose of Use Library Resources (Students)

SN	Purposes	No. of Respondents	Percentage (n%, n=186)
1	For preparation of class notes	179	96.24%
2	For preparation of assignments	111	59.68%
3	For preparation of exam	163	87.63%
4	For personal research	17	9.14%
5	To find course related resources	85	45.70%
6	For gaining new knowledge	89	47.85%
7	To read in leisure time	54	29.03%
8	Others	12	6.45%

Location of Accessing Library Resources:

This particular multiple-answer question in the survey sought information regarding the preferred place for teachers and students to access library materials.

(a) For Teachers

The preferred location for teachers to utilise library materials is at home (100%), followed by lecture time (82%). In addition, just 56% of teachers use library study rooms to access library resources.

Table 8: Access Location of Library Resources (Teachers)

SN	Access Location	No. of Respondents	Percentage (n%, n=50)
1	Library Study Room	28	56.00%
2	Staff Cabin	34	68.00%
3	At Lecture	41	82.00%
4	Home	50	100.00%
5	Other	0	0.00%

(b) For Students

For the utilisation of library resources, students favour library study rooms and classrooms for the use of library resources

(100%). Preference to use library resources at home is average (60.22%), while only 12.90% choose hostels.

Table 9: Access Location of Library Resources (Teachers)

SN	Access Location	No. of Respondents	Percentage (n%, n=186)
1	Library Study Room	186	100.00%
2	Classroom	186	100.00%
3	Hostel	24	12.90%
4	Home	112	60.22%
5	Other	33	17.74%

Frequency of Use Library Resources:

This question of the questionnaire examined about the use frequency of several types of library materials. This question further subdivided into following two types.

(a) By Document Type

Table 10 displays responses in which users select their preferred document type from Print and Electronic resources. The majority of teachers frequently used print resources (74%), while all of them used electronic resources. Students utilised electronic resources (76.35%) more frequently than print resources (63.98%).

Table 10: Use Frequency of Library Resources (by document types)

Use Frequency	Print Resources		E-Resources	
	Teacher (n%, n=50)	Students (n%, n=186)	Teacher (n%, n=50)	Students (n%, n=186)
Always	13 (26.00%)	119 (63.98%)	50 (100.00%)	142(76.35%)
Often	37 (74.00%)	52 (27.96%)	0 (0.00%)	24 (12.90%)
Sometimes	0 (0.00%)	15 (8.06%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (10.75%)
Rarely	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Never	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)

(b) By Resource Type

The following two tables (Table 11 and Table 12) further examined the use frequency of each type of available library material by the teachers and the students.

Among Teachers

All of the respondents (teachers) consistently (100%) chose subject- and course-specific books and research journals among the options. Similarly, some of the teachers never used resources like indexing/abstracting collection, subject encyclopaedia, maps, CDs, etc.

Table 11: Use Frequency of Each Library Resources (by teachers)

Resource Type	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Text Books	11 (22.00%)	31 (62.00%)	8 (16.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Subject/Course Specific Books	50 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Competitive Books	0 (0.00%)	5 (10.00%)	21 (42.00%)	10 (20.00%)	14 (28.00%)
General/Fiction Books	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (18.00%)	29 (58.00%)	12 (24.00%)
Research Journals	50 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Indexing/Abstracting Collection	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (100.00%)
Conference Proceedings	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	43 (86.00%)	7 (14.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Research Reports	10 (20.00%)	22 (44.00%)	12 (24.00%)	6 (12.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Preprints	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (100.00%)
Magazines	33 (66.00%)	5 (10.0%)	9 (18.00%)	3 (6.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Subject Encyclopaedia	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (100.00%)
Language Dictionary	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (8.00%)	46 (92.00%)

Table 11 To Be Continued...

Statistical Sources	2 (4.00%)	23 (46.00%)	15 (30.00%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (20.00%)
Theses and Dissertation	17 (34.00%)	33 (66.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Govt. Publications	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (100.00%)
Year Books	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (4.00%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (96.00%)
Gazetteers	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (100.00%)
Maps	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (100.00%)
CDs	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (100.00%)
Newspapers	0 (0.00%)	32 (64.00%)	12 (24.00%)	6 (12.00%)	0 (0.00%)

Among Students

The majority of the student respondents preferred reading subject- and course-specific books (95.70%). Magazines

(72.58%) and textbooks (83.33%) come in second and third. Like some teachers, some students never used materials like subject encyclopaedias, dictionaries, maps, etc.

Table 12: Use Frequency of Each Library Resources (by students)

Resource Type	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Text Books	155 (83.33%)	31 (16.67%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Subject/Course Specific Books	178 (95.70%)	8 (4.30%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Competitive Books	61 (32.80%)	94 (50.54%)	20 (10.75%)	6 (3.23%)	5 (2.69%)
General/Fiction Books	56 (30.11%)	54 (29.03%)	59 (31.72%)	7 (3.76%)	10 (5.38%)
Research Journals	19 (10.22%)	25 (13.44%)	106 (56.99%)	11 (5.91%)	25 (13.44%)
Indexing/Abstracting Collection	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	27 (14.52%)	35 (18.82%)	124 (66.67%)
Conference Proceedings	73 (39.25%)	42 (22.58%)	49 (26.34%)	18 (9.68%)	4 (2.15%)
Research Reports	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	52 (27.96%)	13 (6.99%)	121 (65.05%)
Preprints	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
Magazines	135 (72.58%)	7 (3.76%)	44 (23.66%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Subject Encyclopaedia	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
Language Dictionary	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
Statistical Sources	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
Theses and Dissertation	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (8.07%)	151 (81.18%)	20 (10.75%)
Govt. Publications	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
Year Books	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
Gazetteers	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
Maps	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (100.00%)
CDs	14 (7.53%)	11 (5.91%)	83 (44.62%)	70 (37.63%)	8 (4.30%)
Newspapers	28 (15.05%)	17 (9.14%)	74 (39.78%)	12 (6.45%)	55 (29.57%)

Frequency of Use Different E-Resources

Broadly, the DCE library has subscribed to four (4) databases of e-resources. Table 13

and Table 14 shows the use frequency of those databases by respondent teachers and students.

(a) By Teachers

The ASME database is only ever utilised by a maximum of 70% of teachers, while IEL

Online is often used by 58%. Global periodicals.com had the lowest usage rate out of the four databases.

Table 13: Use Frequency of E-Resources (by teachers)

E-Resources	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
IEL Online	16 (32.00%)	29 (58.00%)	5 (10.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
ASME (including AMR)	35 (70.00%)	2 (4.00%)	10 (20.00%)	3 (6.00%)	0 (0.00%)
InfoTrac Engineering Collection (IEC)	11 (22.00%)	19 (38.00%)	7 (14.00%)	13 (26.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Global Periodicals.com	0 (0.00%)	1 (2.00%)	42 (84.00%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (14.00%)

(b) By Students

For the student, IEL online is the most preferable database with 57.53% always users. For the positive usage side, InforTrac

Engineering Collection and ASME followed it. And, similar to teachers, Global Periodicals.com had the lowest usage rate.

Table 14: Use Frequency of E-Resources (by students)

E-Resources	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
IEL Online	107 (57.53%)	20 (10.75%)	54 (29.03%)	5 (2.69%)	0 (0.00%)
ASME (including AMR)	36 (19.35%)	112 (60.21%)	19 (10.22%)	2 (1.08%)	17 (9.14%)
InfoTrac Engineering Collection (IEC)	58 (31.18%)	63 (33.87%)	45 (24.20%)	12 (6.45%)	8 (4.30%)
Global Periodicals.com	49 (26.34%)	32 (17.20%)	2 (1.08%)	63 (33.87%)	40 (21.51%)

Satisfaction Level with the Available Library Resources:

For Print resources, a maximum of 42% of teachers choose a neutral position, while the

students are satisfied with 47.31% coverage. Whereas, with the available E-resources, 42% of teachers were very satisfied and the same trend goes for students (59.68%).

Table 15: Satisfaction Level with the Available Library Resources

Satisfaction Level	Print Resources		E-Resources	
	Teacher (n%)	Students (n%)	Teacher (n%)	Student (n%)
Very Satisfied	9 (20.00%)	54 (29.03%)	21 (42.00%)	111 (59.68%)
Satisfied	13 (26.00%)	88 (47.31%)	19 (38.00%)	20 (10.75%)
Neutral	21 (42.00%)	28 (15.06%)	9 (18.00%)	48 (25.81%)
Dissatisfied	0 (0.00%)	16 (8.60%)	2 (4.00%)	4 (2.15%)
Extremely Dissatisfied	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.61%)

Problem Faced during Use of Library Resources:

Table 16 displays the problems faced by the teachers or the students while accessing library resources. The absence of useful resources and an outdated selection are cited by all teachers (100%) as the most pressing

issues with the existing library collection. In addition to these, a lack of awareness was noted as a significant barrier to obtaining necessary resources. Lack of valuable materials (79.57%) and limited seating (69.89%) were the main barriers for students to use library resources.

Table 16: Problem Faced during Use of Library Resources

SN	Problems	No. of Respondents	
		Teachers (n%)	Students (n%)
1	Lack of Valued Resources	50 (100.00%)	148 (79.57%)
2	Lack of Course Relevant Resources	13 (26.00%)	44 (23.66%)
3	Lack of Updated Collection	50 (100.00%)	102 (54.84%)
4	Inadequate Internet Facility	0 (0.00%)	9 (4.84%)
5	Insufficient Seating Facility	4 (8.00%)	130 (69.89%)
6	Lack of Awareness	37 (74.00%)	105 (56.45%)
7	Poor Library Services	16 (32.00%)	52 (27.96%)
8	Lack of Support by Library Staff	11 (22.00%)	0 (0.00%)
9	Library Rules/ Procedure	6 (12.00%)	94 (50.54%)
10	Others	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

On the basis of above analysis, the following are the major findings of this study,

- (i) The majority of the teachers often visit the library, whereas the students always visit the library.
- (ii) Overall, students are more aware of the library resources than the teachers.
- (iii) The teachers preferred self-awareness, but the students required the help of library staff regarding the knowledge of library resources.
- (iv) The preparation of lectures is the most preferred reason for a teacher to use library resources, and that is the preparation of class notes for the students.
- (v) Almost all of the respondent teachers preferred to use library resources at home, whereas the students preferred library study rooms or classrooms.
- (vi) Both the teachers and the students prioritise online resources more than print resources.
- (vii) For the teachers, subject/course related books and research journals are the most favourable library resources; students like textbooks most besides subject/course related books.
- (viii) ASME (including AMR) is the teacher's favourite online database, and students preferred IEL Online the most.

(ix) In the case of the print collection, teachers are neutrally satisfied, but the students are overall satisfied with it. The online library collection, on the other hand, successfully satisfied both.

(x) Teachers choose the lack of valued and updated resources as the prime issue in the current library collection, whereas the student's lack of insufficient internet facility comes to next the lack of valued resources.

SUGGESTIONS

The following actions can be made to enhance library utilisation and enhance user satisfaction:

- (i) Rather than purchasing a large number of inexpensive resources from a local publisher, more valuable international collections should be purchased.
- (ii) Old collections that are used mostly, should be updated with newer editions.
- (iii) The number of copies should be increased for the highly demanded books.
- (iv) The library ought to give demand-driven acquisition more authority.
- (v) Online databases must include information on every facet of a given stream, and multidisciplinary databases should subscribe after being properly assured of its inclusion.

- (vi) The library needs to have access to a more robust internet facility.
- (vii) It is important to periodically offer orientations, seminars, and outreach initiatives to inform patrons of the library's services and resources.

CONCLUSION

Computers and communication infrastructure are necessities in the information age, thus libraries must give more significant funding and skilled staff to sustain and improve services to engineering college library users. The arrangement of information services in engineering college libraries demands new technology and ways to serve the users because of the enormous increase of knowledge and its dissemination through a wide range of media. Information is now considered to be a crucial resource. It is essential for decision-making, knowledge expansion, and the preservation of research endeavours. [17]

A study of library users always uncovers certain flaws in a library's current procedures; it is a more tangible way to assess the system in place, make adjustments, and create a targeted strategy in response. The current study has done the same, and it has discovered that the DCE library lacks a valued and up-to-date collection while having a significant number and variety of library resources. Additionally, the availability of the internet and public knowledge are factors in the limited use of library resources. It is clear that the library is not doing enough to make use of the resources it has purchased.

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